

On Continual Classes of Evolution Equations

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(Received 10 June, 2025)

The original Miura transformation, considered as a nonlinear potential transformation, is applicable to a continual class of evolution equations, not only to discrete integrable equations and their hierarchies. The same continual class of evolution equations appears from a different problem, namely, from the gauge-invariant description of a zero-curvature representation with a definite x -part containing no essential parameter.

PACS numbers: 02.30.Ik, 02.30.Jr

Keywords: evolution equations, Miura transformation, zero-curvature representations

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17243012>

1. Introduction

The original Miura transformation was introduced in [1] as a nonlinear potential transformation relating the Korteweg–de Vries (KdV) equation to the modified KdV equation. The Miura transformation is applicable not only to the KdV equation and its integrable hierarchy. For example, the Sawada–Kotera equation and the Kaup–Kupershmidt equation also admit the Miura transformation [2]. Moreover, as we have shown in [3], the Miura transformation is applicable to a very wide (continual) class of evolution equations, and most of those equations, of course, should be non-integrable in any reasonable sense. Let us note that this result of [3] was inspired by the Lie–Bäcklund algebra structure of the exactly solvable Liouville equation.

In the present paper, in Section 2, we recall the direct derivation of the complete class of evolution equations admitting the Miura transformation, without any reference to Lie–Bäcklund algebras. In Section 3, we show that exactly the same continual class of evolution equations appears from a different problem, namely, from the gauge-invariant description of a zero-curvature representation with a definite

x -part containing no essential parameter. In Section 4, we comment on the obtained results.

2. The Miura transformation

Let us find all the local evolution equations

$$u_t = f(x, t, u, u_1, \dots, u_n) \quad (1)$$

which admit the Miura transformation

$$u = v_1 - \frac{1}{2}v^2, \quad (2)$$

where u_i and v_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots$) denote $\partial_x^i u$ and $\partial_x^i v$, respectively.

The Miura transformation (2) relates a local evolution equation (1) to a local evolution equation

$$v_t = g(x, t, v, v_1, \dots, v_n) \quad (3)$$

if the function $u(x, t)$ determined by (2) satisfies (1) whenever the function $v(x, t)$ satisfies (3). This can be equivalently expressed by the condition

$$\begin{aligned} & f(x, t, u, u_1, \dots, u_n) \\ &= (D_x - v)g(x, t, v, v_1, \dots, v_n), \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where D_x denotes the total derivative with respect to x . Note that the condition (4) must be a differential consequence of the relation (2),

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otherwise (4) and (2) would produce an ordinary differential equation restricting solutions v of the evolution equation (3).

Now, using the relation (2) and its differential consequences, namely, $v_1 = u + \frac{1}{2}v^2$, $v_2 = u_1 + uv + \frac{1}{2}v^3$, $v_3 = u_2 + u^2 + u_1v + 2uv^2 + \frac{3}{4}v^4$, etc., we can eliminate v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{n+1} from the condition (4), and in this way we rewrite (4) in the following equivalent form:

$$f(x, t, u, u_1, \dots, u_n) = (\tilde{D}_x - v)h(x, t, v, u, u_1, \dots, u_{n-1}), \tag{5}$$

where

$$\tilde{D}_x = \partial_x + (u + \frac{1}{2}v^2)\partial_v + u_1\partial_u + u_2\partial_{u_1} + u_3\partial_{u_2} + \dots \tag{6}$$

and

$$h(x, t, v, u, u_1, \dots, u_{n-1}) = g(x, t, v, \tilde{D}_x v, \tilde{D}_x^2 v, \dots, \tilde{D}_x^n v). \tag{7}$$

The crucial point is that the condition (5) must be an identity, because it cannot be a differential consequence of the relation (2). Therefore, the right-hand side of (5) must be independent of v , this determines admissible functions h , and then (5) is simply a definition of admissible functions f .

Next, repeatedly applying ∂_v to (5) three times and using the evident identity

$$\partial_v \tilde{D}_x = (\tilde{D}_x + v)\partial_v, \tag{8}$$

we obtain the auxiliary condition

$$(\tilde{D}_x + 2v)\partial_v^3 h = 0. \tag{9}$$

Since h must be a local expression, it follows from (9) that $\partial_v^3 h = 0$, that is, the function h is necessarily of the form

$$h = \frac{1}{2}v^2 p + vq + r, \tag{10}$$

where p, q and r are functions of $x, t, u, u_1, \dots, u_{n-1}$.

Finally, substituting the expression (10) into the condition (5) and taking into account that p, q, r and f do not depend on v , we obtain the following expressions:

$$q = D_x p, \quad r = (D_x^2 + u)p, \\ f = (D_x^3 + 2uD_x + u_1)p, \tag{11}$$

where p is an arbitrary function of $x, t, u, u_1, \dots, u_{n-3}$. The relations (7), (10) and (11) solve our problem. We have found that the local evolution equations (1) admitting the Miura transformation (2) constitute the continual class

$$u_t = (D_x^3 + 2uD_x + u_1) \times p(x, t, u, u_1, \dots, u_{n-3}), \tag{12}$$

the corresponding local evolution equation (3) being

$$v_t = (D_x^2 + vD_x + v_1) \times p(x, t, v_1 - \frac{1}{2}v^2, D_x(v_1 - \frac{1}{2}v^2), \dots, D_x^{n-3}(v_1 - \frac{1}{2}v^2)), \tag{13}$$

where the function p and the order n are arbitrary.

3. The zero-curvature representation

The continual class of evolution equations (12) appears from a completely different problem as well. Let us find all the local evolution equations (1) which admit zero-curvature representations (ZCRs)

$$D_t X - D_x T + [X, T] = 0 \tag{14}$$

with the fixed matrix X given by

$$X = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & u \\ -\frac{1}{2} & 0 \end{pmatrix} \tag{15}$$

and any 2×2 traceless matrices $T(x, t, u, u_1, \dots, u_{n-1})$, where D_t and D_x stand for the total derivatives, the square brackets denote the matrix commutator, and $u_i = \partial_x^i u$

($i = 1, 2, \dots$). We solve this problem by the cyclic basis method [4–9].

In the present case of the matrix X given by (15), the characteristic form of the ZCR (14) of an evolution equation (1) is

$$fC = \nabla T, \quad (16)$$

where f is the right-hand side of (1), $C = \partial X / \partial u$, and the operator ∇ is defined as $\nabla M = D_x M - [X, M]$ for any 2×2 matrix M . Computing C , ∇C , $\nabla^2 C$ and $\nabla^3 C$, we find that the cyclic basis is $\{C, \nabla C, \nabla^2 C\}$, with the closure equation

$$\nabla^3 C = -u_1 C - 2u \nabla C. \quad (17)$$

Decomposing T over the cyclic basis as

$$T = a_0 C + a_1 \nabla C + a_2 \nabla^2 C, \quad (18)$$

where a_0 , a_1 and a_2 are functions of $x, t, u, u_1, \dots, u_{n-1}$, we find from (16) and (17) that

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 &= -D_x a_2, & a_0 &= -D_x a_1 + 2u a_2, \\ f &= D_x a_0 - u_1 a_2. \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Note that the function $a_2 = p(x, t, u, u_1, \dots, u_{n-3})$ and the order n remain undetermined. The explicit expressions

$$T = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} D_x p & D_x^2 p + u p \\ -\frac{1}{2} p & -\frac{1}{2} D_x p \end{pmatrix} \quad (20)$$

and

$$f = D_x^3 p + 2u D_x p + u_1 p, \quad (21)$$

which follow from (18) and (19), solve our problem.

We have found that the local evolution equations (1) admitting ZCRs (14) with the matrix X given by (15) constitute the continual class (12), the corresponding matrices T being determined by (20).

4. Conclusion

We have shown that the original Miura transformation (2), considered as a nonlinear potential transformation, is applicable to a continual class of evolution equations (12), not only to discrete integrable equations and their hierarchies. We have also shown that exactly the same continual class of evolution equations (1) with (21) appears from a different problem, namely, from the gauge-invariant description of a zero-curvature representation (14) with the given x -part (15) containing no essential parameter.

Not every expression of the form $u = s(x, t, v, v_1, \dots, v_m)$ can serve as a Miura-type transformation between two local evolution equations, as was shown by a simple polynomial generalization of the original (quadratic) Miura transformation [10]. In many interesting special cases, the general Miura-type transformations can be analyzed and represented as chains of simpler transformations [11], and this definitely deserves further investigation. We believe that the relation between the differential substitutions (another name of Miura-type transformations) and the so-called pseudosymmetries [12] may be very useful, for the following reason. Pseudosymmetries correspond to ZCRs with some fixed x -parts [12], whereas ZCRs with fixed x -parts always represent some continual classes of evolution equations [4].

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